

Bridging Nature and Culture: Fostering Next-Generation Sustainability Leadership

IPBES Fellows-Future Earth Workshop Report

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Report of the three-day workshop and a ‘Conversations with the Earth: Celebrating Biodiversity through the Arts’ Evening convened at the 6th IPBES Plenary, Medellín, Colombia (17-24 March 2018). The event brought together a global transdisciplinary team of emerging biodiversity and ecosystem services experts to shape transformative thinking about the relationships between nature and human well-being, with a particular focus on the role of culture and Nature’s Contributions to People.

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Executive Summary

Next-generation sustainability leadership is essential for [global sustainable development](#) and [transformative action towards sustainability](#) on a [dynamic planet](#). The Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) (a [Future Earth Strategic Partner](#)), is the intergovernmental body which assesses the state of biodiversity and ecosystem services. The IPBES conceptual framework recognises culture as an important component in the co-production of Nature's Contribution to People. With a focus on culture and with arts-based approaches as our entry point, we convened a global transdisciplinary team of emerging biodiversity and ecosystem services experts to shape transformative thinking about the relationships between nature and human well-being. Activities centred on a 3-day workshop and a 'Conversations with the Earth: Celebrating Biodiversity through the Arts' Evening ('Biodiversity Meets the Arts' Evening) at the 6th IPBES Plenary in Medellín, Colombia from 17-24 March 2018.

Activities in Medellín were structured around 4 Objectives:

Objective 1: Develop transformative interdisciplinary scholarship for sustainability-related decision-making by articulating a research agenda for the future of biodiversity;

Objective 2: Define a strategy for intergenerational continuity within IPBES which harnesses investments in the IPBES Fellowship programme;

Objective 3: Facilitate sensitivity and inclusion of different cultural work and leadership styles within IPBES and other international assessments;

Objective 4: Apply arts-based approaches to nurture deeper connections between all IPBES stakeholders and nature.

The workshop, 'Biodiversity Meets the Arts' Evening and participation of IPBES Fellows at the 6th Plenary facilitated intergenerational mentorship; built capacity for future leadership of Future Earth and IPBES Assessments; and enabled stakeholder and policy-maker engagement with the IPBES Conceptual Framework.

Immediate outputs include:

- (1) A preliminary research agenda for the future of biodiversity and ecosystem services;
- (2) A preliminary framework for addressing how work style and leadership differences across culture may affect the process and outcome of scientific assessments such as those conducted by IPBES;
- (3) A preliminary strategy outlining the future role of IPBES Fellows within the IPBES process;
- (4) A methodological approach for documenting and interpreting 'different ways of working' within IPBES Assessments;
- (5) Preliminary outlines for further research papers inspired by collaborations during the workshop.

Subsequent outputs will include:

- (1) A journal article which examines the role of culture in global assessments using the results obtained from application of our methodology;
- (2) A research agenda for the future of biodiversity and ecosystem services co-produced with IPBES and Future Earth Natural Assets KAN experts; and
- (3) A strategy for next-generation sustainability leadership within IPBES.

These outputs contribute directly to the aim of the IPBES-Future Earth Partnership to develop robust research to shape global governance and policy to protect the planet's natural support systems for present and future generations.

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Project Description

Background and context

Human activity is pushing our planet beyond sustainable limits (Steffen et al 2015). There is increasing recognition that global sustainability initiatives need to incorporate diverse knowledge systems and worldviews by involving a broader range of stakeholders, disciplines, methods, and tools (Beck et al. 2014). Engagement with the public and policy-makers on sustainability issues is, however, insufficient (Lindenfeld et al. 2012; van der Linden et al. 2015). Moreover, work and leadership styles in global sustainability initiatives tend to favour western approaches over the numerous others that prevail worldwide. Acknowledgement of these shortfalls has led to calls for greater application of participatory approaches in sustainability science (van Kerkhoff & Lebel 2006; Nisbet & Scheufele 2009; Lindenfeld et al. 2012; van der Linden et al. 2015). Inclusion of more tools for amplifying participation needs to be accompanied by transitional changes that are sensitive and conducive to cultural differences in work and leadership styles, decision-making and communication. Early-career experts participating in global sustainability initiatives are uniquely positioned to observe and experience these cultural nuances and to develop novel solutions to address them (Lim et al. 2017).

The Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) assesses the state of biodiversity and nature's contributions to society. The IPBES Fellowship Programme was launched to promote the integration of early-career experts into science-policy interfaces. We, the IPBES Fellows of the Global Assessment, constitute a global transdisciplinary team of sixteen emerging biodiversity and ecosystems services experts. We come from all inhabited continents; ten of us are from developing countries. With disciplinary backgrounds which include ecology, sociology, economic and law we seek to develop transdisciplinary, transformative and solution-oriented approaches to the effective management and governance of biodiversity and its contributions to human well-being.

IPBES aims to provide policy-makers with the tools and methods to protect and sustainably use biodiversity. The IPBES Conceptual Framework, which underpins all activities of the platform, was developed through a two-year co-production process which involved experts from a range of disciplines and knowledge systems as well as over 100 governments and non-governmental organisations (Diaz et al. 2015a). The Conceptual Framework aims to inspire integrated thinking which considers the full cycle of interactions across the complex systems of nature, nature's contributions to people¹, and good quality of life, as well as anthropogenic assets and direct and indirect drivers (Diaz et al. 2018; Diaz et al. 2015b). Culture permeates the Conceptual Framework particularly in terms of how nature, nature's contribution to people, and good quality of life are viewed and how nature's contributions to people is co-produced by people and the environment (Palomo et al., 2016).

The arts and artistic processes are increasingly seen as a key component of interdisciplinary sustainability research (Polfus et al. 2017). The reason for this growing acceptance of arts-based approaches may be found in the limitations of traditional scientific methods in integrating knowledge with emotion and action (Heras & Tàbara 2014, 2016). The arts can help supplement cognitive registers with emotional ones and stimulate interest in sustainability issues (Osnes 2013; Fernández-Llamazares & Cabeza 2017). The arts also have an important role in promoting intercultural interaction (Wesley 2007; OMC Working Group 2014). The emergence of these artistic modes of inquiry reflects a shift in the conception of the arts not only as an emotional expression of the human condition, but as an essential form of knowledge within the intersection of multiple disciplines and methods (Eisner 2008; Leavy 2009). This is also reflected in a recent [special feature](#) in *Ecology and Society* titled "Reconciling Art and Science for Sustainability" dedicated to exploring the multiple ways that art can advance sustainability discourse.

¹ Nature's Contributions to People (NCP) was referred to as Nature's benefit to people in earlier iterations of the Conceptual Framework including Diaz et al. (2015a,b). The concept has been further developed and re-named: Nature's Contributions to People (NCP)(Pascual et al., 2017; IPBES 2017).

Nisbet and Scheufele (2009) emphasise the importance of enabling the public to engage directly within the social, ethical and economic implications of a scientific topic. Meanwhile, van der Linden et al. (2015) find that the human brain privileges emotional connections and experiences over analytical processes when making decisions. They also identify social norms as a powerful source of influence. van der Linden et al. (2015) therefore highlight the need to appeal to and leverage the social context. Arts-based approaches have the potential to support social learning processes in sustainability, fostering a transdisciplinary sensibility to deal with social-ecological complexity and facilitating transformative thinking (Guhrs 2006; Kagan 2010, 2011). Polfus et al (2017) demonstrate the potential for visual art to enhance sustainable stewardship of biodiversity by improving communication, participation and knowledge production in interdisciplinary research. At the same time, the arts and artistic processes provide a valuable, yet underexplored, means of addressing social-ecological resilience while engaging the public in planetary sustainability issues (Guy et al. 2015; Rathwell & Armitage 2016; Polfus et al. 2017).

Aim and objectives

The overall aim of this project is to contribute to transformative thinking for the future of biodiversity and human well-being by engaging stakeholders and policy-makers through a focus on culture and the arts. The IPBES Plenary is a key part of the IPBES Assessment process as it is there that governments negotiate and review the assessment text. This work was centred on a 3-day workshop and a ‘Conversations with the Earth: Celebrating Biodiversity through the Arts’ Evening (‘Biodiversity Meets the Arts’ Evening) at the [6th IPBES Plenary, Medellín, Colombia](#) (17-24 March 2018). We built on the role of culture within the IPBES framework while adopting arts-based processes to foster deeper connections with biodiversity and stakeholders. In doing so we capitalised on:

- existing intergenerational partnerships within the IPBES process which are aimed at developing tomorrow’s sustainability leaders;
- key findings of a recently submitted paper on intergenerational partnerships (co-authored by all 16 Global Assessment Fellows) and
- the [outcomes of the Future Earth Network of Networks- IPBES webinar](#) .

The workshop objectives are as follows:

Objective 1: Develop transformative interdisciplinary scholarship for sustainability-related decision-making by articulating a research agenda for the future of biodiversity;

Objective 2: Define a strategy for intergenerational continuity within IPBES which harnesses investments in the IPBES Fellowship programme;

Objective 3: Facilitate sensitivity and inclusion of different cultural work and leadership styles within IPBES and other international assessments;

Objective 4: Apply arts-based approaches to nurture deeper connections between all IPBES stakeholders and nature.

The workshop and participation of IPBES Fellows in the 6th Plenary proposed activities aimed to strengthen linkages between IPBES and Future Earth particularly among the next-generation of IPBES and Future Earth leaders. The subsequent outputs will contribute directly to the aim of the IPBES-Future Earth Partnership to develop robust research to shape global governance and policy to protect the planet’s natural support systems for present and future generations.

Activities and outputs

Workshop

The 3-day workshop and 'Biodiversity Meets the Arts' Evening addressed each of the objectives set out above. A graphic facilitator ([ConverSketch](#)) was engaged to enable transformative systems thinking for the development and communication of Objectives 1 & 2. Graphic facilitation is a form of visual note-taking which involves illustration of large figures that reflect discussions and capture the ideas and feelings of participants (see for e.g. Figure 2 below). The graphic facilitator interprets and links information and thus nurtures new understandings of the issues discussed and the connections between these issues (Espiner & Hartnett 2016). Graphic facilitation has therefore been used in many different contexts including in fostering systems thinking (Espiner & Hartnett 2016).

The use of a graphic facilitator at the Medellín workshop not only taps into the capacity for art and art-making to act as a catalyst for interdisciplinary research (see Polfus et al. 2017 discussion above); the illustrations produced also provide engaging communication outputs.

Objective 1: Research Agenda for the future of biodiversity

The output of this objective will be an agenda of key research questions for the development of sustainable futures for biodiversity and ecosystem services.

Objective 2: Strategy for intergenerational continuity within IPBES

The [Future Earth Early Career Network of Networks – IPBES Webinar](#) facilitated dialogue between Fellows and online participants (Figure 1) about how best to utilise the skills and experience that Fellows have developed through involvement in the authorship of the IPBES Assessments. Similar discussions are on-going within the IPBES leadership and the Capacity-Building Technical Support Unit surrounding how best to maintain the IPBES Fellowship network once the Assessments have ended. This objective contributes to and builds on both these discussions.

The output of this objective is a strategy for next-generation leadership within IPBES which harnesses the investment in the IPBES Fellows programme while fostering intergenerational continuity and retaining institutional memory. This was developed and visualised with the Graphic Facilitator at the Medellín workshop. The workshop also resulted in the formation of an Alumni Network consisting of all IPBES Fellows.

Objective 3: Facilitate sensitivity and inclusion of different cultural work and leadership styles within IPBES and other international assessments

Today, effective leadership requires not just learning to work effectively with people from a wide range of cultural backgrounds, but also having the skillset to help multi-cultural groups collaborate effectively with one another. For IPBES assessments to be successful, it is paramount that assessment authors and support teams are capable of navigating through the different cultural realities of how people think and get things done. Unless participants know how to decode other cultures and avoid easy-to-fall-into cultural traps, the assessment process is vulnerable to inefficiency, teams that are unable to work together, and assessments that do not fully deliver on the inclusiveness aspect. Consequently, the purpose of Objective 3 was to explore whether cultural differences in work and leadership styles have influenced the experience and outcomes of IPBES Assessments (Thematic, Regional and Global) while engaging with the broader literature on inter-cultural dialogues in sustainability decision-making (e.g. Borie & Hulme 2015; Corbera et al. 2016; Tengö et al. 2017).

The half-day workshop in Medellín included all IPBES fellows from each of the IPBES Assessments (Regional, Thematic and Global) and focused on cross-cultural management. The session was led by cross-cultural management expert, Karen Cvitkovich. Karen introduced participants to a model of cultural dimensions which facilitates measurement and understanding of national trends and individual behaviour. Fellows received first-hand experience on decoding how people think, lead, and get things done when working in an international environment, and to develop strategies to manage these differences effectively. Brief lectures followed by interactive sessions and discussion. The use of exercises, multimedia and anecdotes emphasised the specific conceptual framework of “The Culture Map” (Meyers 2014). The session was founded on demonstrating with examples how, while national stereotyping is dangerous, ignoring cultural differences can be fatal. The facilitator also assisted the fellows in thinking through the types of questions that could be included in a survey of IPBES authors aimed at exploring how cultural diversity has played out in completed and ongoing assessments.

Key outputs will include:

1. development and implementation of a survey of IPBES assessment participants on cultural dimensions
2. A set of recommendations for the IPBES internal evaluation which identifies how to incorporate ‘different ways of working’ within IPBES Assessments.
3. A journal article focusing on the key findings of the survey.

The intended outcome of this process is the adoption of identified recommendations e.g. through capacity building on working across cultures for IPBES authors.

Objective 4: Apply arts-based approaches to nurture deeper connections between all IPBES stakeholders and nature

The ‘Biodiversity Meets the Arts’ evening at the IPBES Plenary celebrated the relationships between people and biodiversity through food, music and storytelling.

Objective 1: Research Agenda for the Future of Biodiversity

Objective 1: Research Agenda for the Future of Biodiversity

Michelle Lim, Uttam Babu Shrestha, Pedro Jaureguiberry, Ivis Chan, Anna Sidorovich, Zeenatul Basher

Aim

Develop transformative interdisciplinary scholarship for sustainability-related decision-making by articulating a research agenda for the future of biodiversity

It is important that intergenerational equity is not neglected in science and decision-making. This is not only for reasons of fairness, but also because generational diversity contributes to novel approaches to navigating the uncertainties of global environmental change. For example, achieving sustainability requires an integrated and interdisciplinary approach that incorporates systems thinking. Early-career experts are well positioned to facilitate systems approaches because they are among the first generations of scholars and practitioners to have interdisciplinarity embedded in their training and research. This objective therefore aims to develop a research agenda for biodiversity informed by the views of emerging biodiversity experts from multiple disciplines from around the world. This is achieved through an online survey and enabled by an intensive workshop with a graphic facilitator.

Methods and process

Pre-workshop

The research agenda was co-produced by Fellows of each of the IPBES Assessments; the [Future Earth Early Career Researchers Network of Networks](#) (NoN); and the Young Professional and Early Career Groups of the IUCN (e.g. the Young Professionals and Early Career Groups of the World Commission on Environmental Law; World Commission on Protected Areas; World Commission on Environmental, Economic and Social Policy etc.). An online survey was disseminated through each of these networks.

Seventy responses were received from 31 countries (Figure 1). Data from the survey was collated prior to the workshop and synthesised into 3 clusters: General themes; Indigenous and Local Knowledge (ILK) and the ‘Global South’.

Figure 1. Survey responses were received from countries highlighted in red.

At the workshop

At the workshop, the 16 Fellows of the IPBES Global Assessment worked with graphic facilitator Karina Branson of [Conversketch](#) to define and visualise key questions and options for research and policy-making for the future of biodiversity and ecosystem services. Graphic facilitation is a form of visual note-taking which involves illustration of large figures that reflect discussions and capture the ideas and feelings of participants. The graphic facilitator interprets and links information and thus nurtures new understandings of the issues discussed and the connections between these issues. Graphic facilitation has therefore been used in many different contexts including in fostering systems thinking (Espiner & Hartnett 2016). Karina was engaged to enable transformative systems thinking for the development and communication of Objective 1.

The workshop began with a short presentation of the preliminary results of the survey followed by an open discussion. Workshop participants identified three main lenses for prioritising and further synthesising survey results: novelty, urgency and importance. Workshop participants were then divided into three groups with each group assigned a cluster (general themes; ILK and ‘Global South’). Within each group survey results were prioritised based on whether they were novel, urgent and or important. From this a list of the most relevant results was developed to inform the framing of the research agenda (see outcomes below).

Throughout the workshop, the Graphic Facilitator worked in parallel to develop a figure that captures the relationship between the main topics examined during the workshop. She also facilitated the discussion

Initial feedback on the Agenda was provided by Eduoard Michel (Future Earth -Paris). IPBES and Natural Assets KAN experts and mentors will be invited to provide further feedback following the workshop.

Workshop Outcomes and Outputs

The final output of Objective 1 will be an agenda of key research questions for the development of sustainable futures for biodiversity and ecosystem services. This will take a form similar to the list of Important Questions for the conservation of global biodiversity (Sutherland et al. 2009); marine biodiversity (Parsons et al. 2014); biodiversity, ecosystem services and sustainability (Hossain et al. 2017) and the conditions for effective sustainability-related science-policy processes (Armitage et al., 2015; Corbera et al., 2016; McInerny et al., 2015; Miller et al., 2014). Our point of departure is the novel approaches and perspectives that the global fellows and early-career respondents from around the world bring to defining and addressing key questions for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity. The workshop in Medellín resulted in an initial iteration of this Agenda (See Annex 1).

The use of a graphic facilitator at the Medellín workshop not only tapped into the capacity for art and art-making as a catalyst for interdisciplinary research (Polfus et al. 2017); the illustrations produced also resulted in engaging communication outputs. It is anticipated that final results and the methodology used will be published in a peer-reviewed journal (e.g. *Conservation Biology*).

Figure 2. Research Agenda for the Future of Biodiversity which highlights the importance of multiple knowledge systems; intergenerational and transdisciplinary collaboration and a positive re-framing of biodiversity. Research questions are prioritised through three lenses of novelty, urgency and importance (Karina Branson - ConverSketch). A higher-resolution image is provided as a separate file at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8063843>.

Next steps

Disseminate research agenda to IPBES and Future Earth Natural Assets KAN experts for comment

A consolidated version of the preliminary iteration of the Research Agenda which emerged from the workshop (see Annex 1 below) is being developed. Once this has been done the Research Agenda will be sent to IPBES and Future Earth experts for comment.

Finalise the research agenda

A final research agenda will be developed in response to feedback.

Develop a journal article

A manuscript will be submitted to a peer-reviewed journal article setting out the research agenda and the methodology used to develop the agenda.

Objective 2: Strategy for
Intergenerational Continuity within
IPBES

Objective 2: Strategy for Intergenerational Continuity within IPBES

Ignacio Palomo, Patricio Pliscoff

Aim

Define a strategy for intergenerational continuity within IPBES which harnesses investments in the IPBES Fellowship programme

Figure 3. Graphic representation of the future of IPBES Fellows in IPBES processes and beyond. A higher-resolution image is provided as a separate file at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8063843>.

This report includes the results of an online survey about the IPBES Fellowship Programme (see Appendix 2 for the complete survey) and the results of the sub-workshop for Objective 2 (see Appendix 3 for the sub-workshop agenda). Several photographs of the process are included in Appendix 4.

Methods and process

An online survey was sent to all 49 Fellows of each of the IPBES Assessments (Global, Regional (Asia-Pacific, Americas, Africa, Europe and Central Asia) and Land Degradation. 33 of a total of 49 Fellows (67% response rate) responded to the survey. (See Figures 3 to 6).

In Medellín, all IPBES Fellows worked in sub-groups to explore each of the issues identified in the survey in greater depth.

The Graphic Facilitator captured and synthesised results throughout the process.

Outcomes and outputs

The online survey provided an overview of experiences within the IPBES Fellowship program. This overview is fundamental for extracting lessons to be applied in future Fellowship programs such as for the IPBES Second Working Programme and for the creation of an Alumni Programme.

The main challenges highlighted in the survey were understanding chapter requirements and managing workloads between distant deadlines (Figure 3).

Figure 4. Answers to the question: What are the main challenges you have faced in your role as a Fellow.

Multiple opportunities were highlighted including improving the understanding of science-policy processes, interacting with other IPBES Fellows, expanding professional networks and be exposed to an interdisciplinary community (Figure 4).

Figure 5. Answers to the question: “What are the main opportunities you experienced in your role as a Fellow”.

Most respondents indicated that they would like to be involved in future IPBES assessments as Lead Author (or Coordinating Lead Author), or as an expert in a taskforce group (Figure 5).

Figure 6. Answers to the question “What are the future roles you would like to be actively involved when your engagement as fellow has ended?”.

Finally, developing scientific outputs and disseminating IPBES products were the main future activities selected by Fellows to be engaged once the Assessments are finished (Figure 6).

Figure 7. Answers to the question “What activities would you like to be involved in within the IPBES Fellows Network?”.

All respondents indicated that they would like to continue engaged with IPBES after the reports are published.

The work in sub-groups to explore the results of the survey in-depth resulted in a highly dynamic activity in which Fellows could engage in group discussions to further explore IPBES Fellowship challenges and opportunities and the development of future roles and activities. The table below presents a summary of the main findings from this activity.

Groups	Discussion points
Group 1: Fellowship challenges.	<p>Main challenges discussed were: Lack of resources (funding and others), lack of incentives for mentors, and guidance on how to contribute at the national level to decision-making.</p> <p>Lessons learned: The importance of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - defining the Fellowship programme in more detail; - identifying funding opportunities; - communicating the value of the fellowship; - incentivising mentorship; - diversifying the fellow pool beyond academia (NGO, IPLC, private sector); - fostering synergies between Fellow’s careers and the Fellowship programme; and - receiving an institutional letter from IPBES to support IPBES engagement.
Group 2: Fellowship opportunities.	<p>Main opportunities discussed were the opportunities to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - contribute to the assessment process; - be part of the IPBES Network; - co-develop scientific papers; - develop long-lasting human connections; - extend beyond one’s comfort zone; - develop new insights and research agendas; and - facilitate national assessments.
Group 3: Future roles.	<p>Main roles discussed were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - being lead author or specialist of a task force. <p>How to get there?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - continue publishing; - be engaged in assessments; - contact country focal points; - develop a comprehensive database of IPBES experts explicit; - develop a Fellows website, common CV for all Fellows, a platform for IPBES alumni: webpage within IPBES;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - develop a guide for future Fellows.
<u>Group 4:</u> Dissemination.	<p>Multiple dissemination activities were discussed and proposed and different target audiences were identified. These included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - dissemination of assessments within Fellow’s institutions; - preparation of communication materials (or use IPBES ones), - translating IPBES results for Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities; - a share-folder to share power point presentations; and - capitalising on new communication channels.
<u>Group 5:</u> Future academic activities.	<p>The main activities discussed were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - further exploration of the role of culture in science-policy processes; - examination of how have science-policy processes have changed across time; - mapping research topics of global institutions and IPBES reports and see matches and gaps, tracking the progress of fellows to measure the impact of the fellowship programme, assessing scientific co-production in science-policy processes (i.e with Indigenous and Local Knowledge) and developing a special issue in Frontiers journals that would provide funds for a conference afterwards.

Working with the graphic facilitator was a highly useful experience to further explore the Fellowship and Alumni Programmes of IPBES. The product of the graphic facilitation (Figure 2), was displayed during the IPBES Plenary in front of the Plenary room, which helped enhance the visibility of the IPBES Programme.

In order to coordinate the IPBES Alumni Network two Fellows, Mireia Valle Tobar (Americas Assessment) and Odirilwe Selomane (Global Assessment) were selected during the last day of the meeting.

Next steps

An on-line platform dedicated to the future IPBES Fellows and IPBES Alumni is planned to increase the visibility of the Fellowship and Alumni Programmes and to facilitate the coordination of their activities.

There are several on-going academic publications that have benefited greatly from the Future Earth-IPBES meeting. The topics of these range from the different understandings of Nature in different languages, developing a future research agenda, assessing indicators of different degrees of participation in IPBES by different countries and the role of culture in science-policy processes.

A document synthesizing the results of the Assessment of the Americas for a broad audience focusing specially on kids from Mexico has been planned to achieve societal outreach and the communication of IPBES results to broader audiences. Also, there are on-going discussions regarding a potential event communicating IPBES results at the Ecosystem Services Partnership Conference in San Sebastian, Spain in 2018.

From this, the Fellows have submitted a ‘fellows’ poster’ to be presented at regional conferences across all regions in October and potentially a session at a global conference in 2019.

Photographs of the process

Figure 8. Pedro Jaureguiberry (IPBES Fellow) and Ingunn Storrø (IPBES TSU) presenting results.

Figure 9. Cosmas Lambini (IPBES Fellow) and Ingunn Storrø (IPBES TSU) presenting results.

Figure 10. Sketch of ideas collected as part of Objective 2: Defining a strategy for intergenerational continuity within IPBES (Sketch by Karina Branson).

LESSON LEARNED

- # Funding Opportunities
- # Communicating Value of fellowship
- # Retain institutional knowledge
- # Incentives for mentorship
- # Commitment from BES to Capacity Building
- # ~~IN~~ DIVERSIFY FELLOWSHIP (BEYOND ACADEMIC COMMUNITY) e.g., PRIVATE SECTOR ILK

DISSEMINATION

- OUR OWN INSTITUTIONS
- PARTNER WITH NATIONAL LOCAL POINTS TO COOPERATE WITH OTHER WORKING INSTITUTIONS
- COMMUNICATION CHANNELS: IDENTIFY AUDIENCES
- TED-ED: BROAD AUDIENCES
- SOCIAL-MEDIA:
 - REACH HIGHLY INFLUENTIAL PEOPLE TO HELP SPREAD MESSAGE (LEARNED & UNLEARNED)
 - ICE-BUCKET CHALLENGE (VIRAL)
 - PLANT DATE TREE
- IN-PERSON MEETINGS AT LOCAL SCALES
- ENGAGE WITH THE PRESS: COMMUNICATION TOOL BOARD, GAMES, SCHOOL MATERIAL
- SCHOOLS, TEACHERS, KIDS: PRACTICAL (GAMES) SCHOOL MATERIAL
- CLOSEST OPES: FAMILY & FRIENDS (POSTERS FROM THEM)
- THINGS WE DO EVERYDAY AS BIO DIVERSITY COORDINATORS AT RESILIENCE CONFERENCE
- BROAD MEDIA: LOCAL RADIO LOCAL NEWSPAPERS NEWS LETTERS
- EUROPE RESEARCH NIGHT (Yearly, autumn)
- DIVIDE INFORMATION

Handwritten notes on the right side of the page:

- KIDS & SCHOOLS
- CIVIL SOCIETY ADULTS
- POLICY-MAKERS
- NGOs
- ACADEMIA
- IPLC
- PEOPLE WITH SOCIAL RESILIENCE
- BROAD AUDIENCES
- FACTS
- LOYALTY

Figures 11 & 12. Results of working group discussions: Lessons learned (Group 1) and dissemination strategies (Group 4).

Objective 3: Facilitate sensitivity and inclusion of different cultural work and leadership styles within IPBES and other international assessments

Objective 3: Facilitate sensitivity and inclusion of different cultural work and leadership styles within IPBES and other international assessments

Tuyeni Mwampamba, Abigail Lynch, Lenke Balint

Aim

Facilitate sensitivity and inclusion of different cultural work and leadership styles within IPBES and other international assessments

It is important that the outputs of IPBES and other international assessments truly reflect the global nature of these initiatives. IPBES recognises the important role of culture in the co-production of Nature's Contribution to People. At the same time, the IPBES Assessment process has gone to great lengths to ensure regional and gender diversity within the authorship teams. The IPBES model for conducting highly inclusive biodiversity and ecosystem services assessments that explicitly recognise and incorporate multiple knowledge systems is exceptional and unique and sets precedence for future assessments. The challenge of bringing together such diversity and reaping the most from what it can offer, however, is still being grappled with in IPBES. What has yet to be explicitly explored in IPBES and other similar assessments, is how working and leadership styles of different cultures are taken into account in the development and implementation of assessments.

Approach

We contracted cultural consultant, Karen Cvitkovich (Mosaic Global Solutions) to facilitate a session during our Medellín workshop on the "Culture Map." In this session, we examined our own cultural profiles (across dimensions of communication, evaluation, leading, deciding, trusting, disagreeing, and scheduling), how cultural dimensions can impact our work in global teams, and discussed strategies for leveraging our diversity within IPBES processes. We also drafted and revised survey questions to consider in the design of a wide-reaching survey that will be sent out to all authors of ongoing and completed IPBES assessments.

Outcomes and outputs

We participated in the "Culture Map" session at our Medellín workshop, produced a IPBES fellows culture map (*see photos below*), received feedback on our draft survey from all the fellows, and aggregated a list of activities to start, stop, and continue based on the session (*see Appendix 4*). The session was very well received by participants and detonated discussions that seem to suggest that cultural differences in working and leadership styles might be playing out in IPBES assessments. It was noted that any exploration of the topic, however, would require a methodology that allowed us to distinguish cultural influences from other processes influencing author interactions such as disciplinary and sectoral 'ways of working' (e.g. social and natural scientists, or scientists and government representatives) or discrepancies in access to infrastructure necessary to participate in assessments (e.g. internet and access to literature).

The Fellows decided that a survey of assessment authors was essential in order to be able to explore this topic further and to go beyond empirical evidence. Several Fellows signed up to be involved in different work-packages aimed at designing, implementing, analysing and communicating the survey and its results.

Figure 13. IPBES Fellow (Lenke Balint) 'mapping' herself across eight cultural dimensions. By having all Fellows do this, we generated a joint map that shows that, even among Fellows there are clear differences in how we approach work, what we expect of leaders, and how we would address a potentially contentious situation with other team members.

Figure 14. The session used role-play, anecdotes and discussions to explore the cultural dimensions of working styles. Here, Fellows explore cultural 'stereotyping' that can generate misunderstanding and misperceptions about others and oneself.

Next steps

The most critical next step is designing and applying the survey. We are in the process of designing the survey with the 'survey development' work package team, a highly interdisciplinary group consisting of Fellows with previous experience in designing, conducting and analysing surveys. The survey will be distributed to assessment authors of completed and ongoing assessments later this year. Karen Cvitkovich, our facilitator in Medellin, has agreed to collaborate with us to ensure that the questions included in the survey enable us to position responses along the cultural dimensions she introduced at the workshop.

Given the recent call by IPBES for input into its next work program for assessments, we will submit a short justification note to the Secretariat for inclusion of cultural dimensions of leadership and working styles into how assessments are done. More specific recommendations will be provided once the survey data has been analysed and interpreted. Specifically, we will use the results of the survey to inform the current IPBES Global Assessment process and provide guidance for future IPBES activities.

We anticipate that the survey will reveal important findings worthy of at least one if not several academic publications. Due to the increasingly interconnected nature of global business, cross-cultural management has become a highly explored topic in the corporate sector. In the science realm, however, it is largely unattended to even as scientific teams become more global and more interdisciplinary in nature. We know that the survey is unprecedented in terms of its size and scope and could be informative to the practice of science. Thus, we will also communicate the findings through additional means (e.g., infographics, videos) to other appropriate audiences.

In addition to designing and applying the survey, the start, stop and continue exercise undertaken at the end of the Culture Map session has also given the Fellows an opportunity for reflection and broader insights into future activities of interest. As presented in Annex 4, these activities broadly revolve around or integrate expressed interest or desires to:

- Better understand cultural differences and how these affect work undertaken in the IPBES context;
- Include and encourage varied ways of thinking and working in collaborative efforts (stemming from cultural as well as personal differences);
- Collaborate, share knowledge and build further networks, within and beyond IPBES

Objective 4: “Arts, Culture and Biodiversity” Evening

Objective 4: “Arts, Culture and Biodiversity” Evening

Álvaro Fernández-Llamazares, Odirilwe Selomane, Aibek Samakov & Ivis Chan

Aim

Apply art-based approaches to nurture deeper connections between all IPBES stakeholders and nature.

The overall aim of our working group was to apply art-based approaches to nurture deeper connections between all IPBES stakeholders and nature. In light of IPBES consideration of culture as an essential component to understand how people relate to nature (e.g., Díaz et al. 2018), we organised an event dedicated to celebrating the profound links between biodiversity and culture and exploring the wonders of biodiversity through a variety of artistic expressions and food.

The event was organized in close collaboration with the Open-Ended Network of IPBES Stakeholders, the Medellín Bureau (Office of Touristic Promotion of the city of Medellín) and the International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN), who partnered with us in sponsoring the event. We sent invitations to over a hundred IPBES country delegates and all registered participants of the IPBES Stakeholders Day. This included Indigenous peoples’ representatives, members of NGOs and the private sector, as well as policy-makers.

Figure 15. IPBES participants and stakeholders watching the performances.

Figure 16. Ingunn Storrø, Head of the IPBES TSU on Capacity-Building welcomes guests.

The event was celebrated on Friday 16 March 18:30-21:00 at the Ballet Nacional el Firulete, a dance school in a neighborhood of Medellín called “Poblado”. To reduce the carbon footprint of the evening, we booked six mini-vans to transport the IPBES Stakeholders from the Intercontinental Hotel in Medellín (where most stakeholders were staying) to the venue. The event was attended by at least 162 people, who had the pleasure of enjoying Colombian vegetarian food, drinks and performances by local artists and IPBES fellows.

The cultural program started with an opening speech by Ingunn Storrø (Head of the IPBES Technical Support Unit on Capacity-Building) and Cristian García (Director of the Ballet Nacional de Danza El Firulete). We then proceeded to the cultural program illustrating the links between biodiversity and culture. All the performances had been conceived to interweave knowledge and emotion in order to foster social reflectivity about, and action towards, sustainability.

Figure 17. Álvaro Fernández-Llamazares, IPBES fellow, sings an environmental song.

Figure 18. Contemporary dance by local dancers.

The cultural program for the evening included, among others, a folktale about wildlife with a Kenyan storyteller (Joyce Ojino), an exhibition of nature photography from mountainous areas in Europe and the Himalayas (Uttam Babu Shrestha and Ignacio Palomo), an environmental protest song on deforestation from the Bolivian Amazon (Álvaro Fernández-Llamazares), a recitation of an excerpt from the *Manas* epic, a cornerstone of Kyrgyz worldview placing nature at the center of life (Aibek Samakov), a reading of a story about nature by a creative writer from Belize (Ivis Chan) and a contemporary dance focusing on the challenges faced by biodiversity in an increasingly human-dominated world (courtesy of the Ballet Nacional El Firulete).

One of the highlights of the cultural program was a performance by the world-renowned and critically-acclaimed band *Casa Kolacho*, which distills the essence of the urban transformation of Medellín. *Casa Kolacho* use the arts as a tool to overcome social problems while transforming marginalized spaces into thriving sustainable communities. The band uses hip-hop, rap and graffiti as “weapons of massive construction” and gave an impassioned case for why it is important to bring in the arts when trying to find the recipe for transformative change towards sustainability. Many of the performances were participatory in nature, with dancers inviting the audience to dance with them, or encouraging participants to do their own sustainability-related graffiti *in vivo*.

Figure 19. Aibek Samakov, IPBES fellow, reciting an excerpt from the *Manas* epic.

Figure 20. Ivis Chan, IPBES fellow, reading of a story about nature.

All the food served in the event was plant-based and had a strong connection with the Colombian landscapes: Colombian wraps with *pico de gallo*, yuca chips, roasted corn, rice pudding with *uchuva* sweet, *patacones* (plantain) with vegetables sautéed in coconut cream, and yellow-corn *arepas* (traditional Colombian pastry). We obtained additional funds from the Norwegian Environmental Protection Agency to cover the costs of all the food and drinks served at the event.

Outcomes and outputs

The event was well-received. Throughout the next few days, participants provided genuine feedback about how they found the event to be both interesting and also an opportunity to reconnect with other IPBES participants in an informal and entertaining way. The event served as a catalyst to discuss multiple ways of using art to communicate more broadly about IPBES and its

outputs to different audiences. This inspired thinking which was captured in “Objective 2: Defining a strategy for intergenerational continuity within IPBES” (Figure 1).

Next steps

One of the ideas collected at the subsequent Objective 2 workshop related to developing innovative communication approaches for disseminating IPBES outputs. The next steps of the process are to continue facilitating the communication of IPBES outcomes, and other avenues of IPBES Fellows work, in ways beyond scientific publications through different media such as videos, art sketches, and music.

We are also planning to write an opinion piece as a call to action aimed at “Bringing the Artists on Board in Sustainability Decision-Making”. A further initiative, indirectly related to the work of this Objective, is a Special Issue on Ethnobiology Through Song in the Journal of Ethnobiology edited by IPBES fellow, Álvaro Fernández-Llamazares. The Special Issue, which includes IPBES participation, will be an important collection of scholarly and heart-felt contributions which illustrate the profound connections between songs, people and nature.

Summary of next steps

Objective 1: Develop transformative interdisciplinary scholarship for sustainability-related decision-making by articulating a research agenda for the future of biodiversity

- 1) Circulate preliminary research agenda to IPBES and Future Earth Natural Assets KAN experts for feedback and further intergenerational dialogue;
- 2) Finalise research agenda;
- 3) Develop outline of journal article setting out the methodology used and our agenda for the future of biodiversity research.

Objective 2: Define a strategy for intergenerational continuity within IPBES which harnesses investments in the IPBES Fellowship programme

- 1) Develop an online platform for future IPBES Fellows and IPBES Alumni to increase visibility of the Fellowship and Alumni Programmes and facilitate coordination of these activities;
- 2) Develop manuscripts inspired by the Objective 2 workshop.

Objective 3: Facilitate sensitivity and inclusion of different cultural work and leadership styles within IPBES and other international assessments

- 1) Incorporate edits and distribute survey to IPBES Global Assessment authors later this year.
- 2) Use the results of the survey to inform the current IPBES Global Assessment process and provide guidance for future IPBES activities.
- 3) Publish the outcomes of this exercise in a peer-reviewed journal and communicate the findings through additional means (e.g., infographics) to other appropriate audiences.

Objective 4: Apply arts-based approaches to nurture deeper connections between all IPBES stakeholders and nature

- 1) Continue facilitating the communication of IPBES outcomes, and other avenues of IPBES Fellows work, in ways beyond scientific publications through different media such as videos, art sketches, and music.
- 2) Opinion piece: “Bringing the Artists on Board”.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Preliminary iteration of the research agenda that emerged from the workshop (Objective 1)

Subgroup A (General research questions regarding the future of biodiversity)

This subgroup discussed on the various issues ranging from the concept of tipping points, social inequality, transboundary impacts (tele-coupling), linear to a circular economy, challenges of communication and bridging knowledge systems. Following questions/research agendas were raised:

- a) Determining tipping points of socio-ecological systems
- b) Exploring the linkages between the social inequality and biodiversity loss as most of the research to-date has investigated the linkage between economic inequality and biodiversity loss
- c) In the hyperconnected world, how are human impacts on the environment distributed across the political and geographic boundaries? How do we minimize and manage the transboundary impact?
- d) Understand the human impacts on the environment while moving from a linear to a circular economy
- e) How can we communicate with positive messages related to biodiversity and environment (given the widespread doom and gloom news/reports about biodiversity loss, environmental degradation)?
- f) How can we bridge different knowledge systems? Can we map the governance and institutional aspects of the IPBES framework?

Subgroup B (inclusion of Indigenous and Local Knowledge (ILK) in science and decision making)

This subgroup discussed inclusion of ILK in decision making and came up with the following research questions/agendas:

- a) What is the status and overall trends of ILK? Given the widespread loss of ILK globally (assumption), what are the likely impacts of ILK loss on the resilience of socio-ecological systems?
- b) What are the reasons for the minimum level of incorporation of ILK into conservation decision-making?
- c) How do we solve the issues of up-scaling the ILK that is mostly local and has a global significance?
- d) Most of the ILK are either undocumented or documented in the form of folklore, songs, story etc (not recognized by the evidence based western science). How do we rationalize the relevance of ILK in the data driven and information heavy world of western science?

Subgroup C (including researchers from global south in science and decision making)

This sub-group started the discussion by revising the existing challenges for the researchers of the global south and status (representation) of the researchers from global south in science and decision-making. It was found that researchers from the global south have limited funding/capacity as well as access to the literature and research platform. To make science and decision making

inclusive, draft research agenda should be multidisciplinary, multicultural, problem-driven and collaborative. This group agreed on the following research questions/agendas:

- a) What is the value of diversity (bringing multiple worldviews)? What are the barriers to including multiple worldviews in science and policy? How do we enhance inclusiveness in science and policy framework by including multiple worldviews?
- b) Given the domination of particular worldviews in science and decision-making (e.g., IPBES framework may not as inclusive as it is supposed to be), what have we missed in our understanding of the human well-being?
- c) What possible changes (definitional, methodological, process-wise etc.) could bring by incorporating different worldviews in science and decision making?
- d) What are the most effective ways to fill the gap in capacity, funding opportunity and access of research materials between global north and south?

Appendix 2 – Survey (Objective 2)

Survey Introduction

Dear IPBES Fellow,

Thanks for your time in completing this survey that will take you less than 15 minutes. It includes two parts. The first includes five questions regarding the IPBES Fellowship Programme and the future roles and activities that IPBES Fellows may be involved in. The second part is for the session on cross-culture management with a facilitator and includes six short questions regarding your nationality, citizenship and mother language. The results of both parts of the survey will help guide the further development of the IPBES Fellowship Programme and will be presented during the IPBES Fellows' workshop in Medellin.

Part 1

Section 1

1. What are the main challenges you have experienced in your role as an IPBES Fellow?

- Funding to attend conferences
- Dealing with IPBES conceptual framework
- Understanding the requirements of my chapter
- Getting used to the dynamics of science-policy processes
- Working in between drafts with distant deadlines
- Other: _____

2. What are the main opportunities you have experienced in your role as an IPBES fellow?

- Interact with other IPBES Fellows and being a part of an IPBES Fellows community
- Expand professional networks with other IPBES Authors
- Improve your understanding of the science-policy processes and their dynamics
- Be exposed to and engaged in an interdisciplinary community of researchers/policy-makers
- Other: _____

Section 2

3. Would you like to continue your involvement in the Network of IPBES Fellows (e.g. IPBES Alumni engagement) after the report in which you have participated has been published?

- Yes
- No

4. What are the future roles you would like to be actively involved when your engagement as fellow has ended?

- Participate in future IPBES Reports as a Fellow,
- Participate in future IPBES Reports as a Contributing Author
- Participate in future IPBES Reports as a Lead Author or Coordinating Lead Author
- Participate in future IPBES Reports as a Reviewer
- Participate in future IPBES Reports as an Expert in a task force (CB, ILK, KID) or specific topic (values etc)

- Participate in future IPBES Reports as a Government representative/IPBES national focal point
- Participate in future IPBES Reports as an IPBES stakeholder (organisations/institutions engaged in and supporting IPBES work)
- Act as a Mentor for future Fellows
- Other: _____

5. What activities would you like to be involved in within the IPBES Fellows Network?

- Engage in dissemination activities and support uptake of IPBES reports
- Raise funding to facilitate the activities of the IPBES Fellows Network (through projects or workshops for example)
- Co-develop scientific outputs (i.e. academic papers, presentation at conferences) based on the work done at IPBES.
- Active engagement in Future Earth Early Career Researchers Network of Networks
- Other: _____

Appendix 3 – Agenda of the Workshop (Objective 2)

Alumni programme for IPBES fellows and Intergenerational continuity within IPBES (Objective 2)

Aim

Understand the perceptions of IPBES Fellows about the challenges and opportunities of being an IPBES Fellow; and identify future roles and activities in which current Fellows can participate as Alumni within IPBES once the reports for which they were elected as Fellows have ended.

Output

Brief report on IPBES Fellows Programme based on a survey and graphics created.

Workplan

Pre-workshop Task

Release online survey to all IPBES Fellows and analyse results.

In-Workshop Task - 17 March 11 am to 16.30 pm

11:00 – 11:30 Introduction to aims of the day

11:30 -12:30 Presentation of survey results and brainstorming among the group to see if there are any additional issues that need to be considered

12:30 – 13:30 Lunch

13:30 – 15:00 Sub-groups (between 4 to 6) to continue discussions around survey topics.

Perhaps each group focuses in one of the questions of the survey. One IPBES Fellow helps facilitate the discussion in each group. Graphic recorder moves in between groups?

15:00 – 16:20 Report back in plenary the results of the sub-group discussions

16:20-16:30 Final remarks and end of the workshop

Graphic recorder produces Graphic describing the IPBES Fellowship Program and ways ahead for IPBES Fellows and IPBES Fellowship Programme.

Presentation of results during the plenary. Perhaps a Canvas or similar artform can be used. Need to coordinate how to get the Graphics printed, format, material, etc.

Development of a short report with results of the processes and future steps

Appendix 4 – ‘Start, Stop, Continue’ Exercise (Objective 3)

Category	Theme	Comment
START	Communication	Precise Communication
START	Communication	Understanding context
START	Culture	Sharing with other IPBES members best practices for intercultural collaboration
START	Culture	Being aware of how cultural differences impact work
START	Culture	Being aware of cultural differences
START	Culture	Reflecting on how culture might contribute to outcomes
START	Culture	Communicating about cultural differences
START	Culture	Discussing more about our cultural backgrounds
START	Culture	taking into account cultural differences
CONTINUE	Culture	Learning on multi-cultural differences and how to navigate them
START	Globalization	Reflecting and recognizing journey from Regional to Global
CONTINUE	Information sharing	Sharing knowledge
CONTINUE	Information sharing	More f2f meeting to share information
START	Initiative	Taking Initiative
START	Innovation	Being creative
CONTINUE	Learning	learning
CONTINUE	Learning	Learning from each other
START	Listen	Listening more
START	Manage	Respect the timeline
START	Networking	Networking
START	Networking	Building new relationships / trust
START	Networking/Collaboration	Cooperation and Networking
START	Networking/Collaboration	To build network for sustainable communication
START	Networking/Collaboration	Learning from each other
CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	Being social
CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	Face-to-face meetings
CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	Looking for different ways to collaborate
CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	Communication and collaboration
CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	Thinking of ways to collaborate into the future / future partnerships
CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	Collaboration
CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	Spirit of friendship
CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	Collaboration
CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	Communication
CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	Collaborating and communication
CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	Collaboration and trust
CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	Collaboration
CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	Cooperation

CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	Collaborating beyond IPBES
CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	Being team players / collaboration
CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	cooperation and working together
CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	Networking and collaboration
CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	Collaboration
CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	Spiritual
CONTINUE	Networking/Collaboration	More cooperation
STOP	Networking/Collaboration	Dominant positions
START	Openness	Being sensitive
START	Openness	Being open minded
START	Openness	Being more welcoming
START	Seek diversity	Interact with different views
START	Seek diversity	Accommodating and enjoying differences
START	Seek diversity	More interaction between groups of fellows
START	Seek diversity	Exploring talents/ skills in team
START	Seek diversity	Deep digging of character and interests
START	Seek diversity	Including more of a variety of fellows in collaborative work
START	Seek diversity	Listening to alternative ideas
START	Seek diversity	Reaching out to people who are different
START	Seek diversity	Give more space to express ideas
CONTINUE	Seek diversity	Considering diversity as an asset and strength
CONTINUE	Seek Diversity	Kindness / inclusion
CONTINUE	Seek diversity	Keeping minds open
STOP	Seek diversity	Stereotypes and assumptions
STOP	Seek diversity	Making excuses due to cultural differences
STOP	Seek diversity	The first assumptions
STOP	Seek diversity	Separating fellows into different special groups
STOP	Seek diversity	Making assumptions
STOP	Seek diversity	Making assumptions
STOP	Seek diversity	Bias
STOP	Seek diversity	Disrespect
STOP	Seek diversity	Separating ourselves into smaller groups when everyone can contribute
STOP	Seek diversity	Expecting everyone to be ok with things suggested - not "one shoe fits all"
STOP	Seek diversity	Being too sensitive on issues like gender, religion and culture
STOP	Seek diversity	Judgemental
STOP	Seek diversity	Making assumptions
STOP	Seek diversity	Making assumptions
STOP	Seek diversity	Prejudice
STOP	Seek diversity	Assuming that culture is not an issue
START	Team	Teambuilding
START	Team	Respecting the team

CONTINUE	Time	Linear time
STOP	Time	Not valuing time
STOP	Time	Wasting time
START	work practices	Applying for project funding as a team
START	work practices	Being flexible
START	work practices	Focus
START	work practices	Naming our children after IPBES :)
START	Work practices	Updating everyone on steps needed
START	work practices	Plan for the future
START	work practices	Finding / building bridges between themes, ideas, topics
START	work practices	New projects and activities
START	work practices	Reach engage more stakeholders, especially private sector, to get real, practical solutions
CONTINUE	work practices	Appreciating our contribution
CONTINUE	Work practices	training
CONTINUE	Work practices	Fellowship programme phase II
CONTINUE	work practices	Work together
CONTINUE	work practices	Joint work and non-labor meetings and interactions
CONTINUE	work practices	meeting regularly
CONTINUE	work practices	working together
CONTINUE	work practices	Working together to support each other as we develop our careers
CONTINUE	Work practices	Precise
CONTINUE	work practices	Exploring how to improves the experience of assessments
STOP	work practices	Treating fellows as interns
STOP	work practices	Not trusting with the talk
STOP	work practices	Silent participation
STOP	work practices	Being dominant
STOP	work practices	Taking people and their behavior for granted
STOP	work practices	Interrupting people when they speak
STOP	work practices	Non-conscious behaviour that could harm others and undermine our potential as a group
STOP	work practices	Interrupt each other and dominate too much
STOP	work practices	Seeing each other as regional or global fellows (it is only a part of who we are)
STOP	work practices	Power dynamics / hierarchies
STOP	work practices	Complaining
STOP	work practices	Putting expectations on others
STOP	work practices	Being silent and waiting for others to initiate
STOP	work practices	Interrupting
STOP	work practices	Communicating the way we are accustomed to